

An African Space Agency: A Proposed Centerpiece of African Union Space Policy

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ABSTRACT

This paper discussed the need for an African Space Agency on the platform of the African Union and further proposed it to be the centerpiece of African Union Space Policy. African Space Program have been in existence for more than fifty (50) years as the first attempt by an African to land on the moon was made in 1964 by a Zambian High School Teacher Edward Mukaka Nkoloso who attempted to surpass the Union of Soviet Socialist Republic's (USSR's) and the United State of America in the race to land on the moon. Although he did not succeed, his ambitious idea gave rise to the numerous Space Programs that Africa boasts of today. This paper examined a Brief History of Space Exploration by the top five (5) African Space Faring Nations that are currently running an Advanced Space Program as well as the African Union Space Policy and Strategy of 2016. The doctrinal method of research was adopted in which books, journals, articles and internet sourced materials were used. The paper also made some findings which includes amongst others the need to establish an African Space Agency that will address current and emerging issues surrounding the African Space Policy of 2016. It was also proposed and recommended that the African Union (AU) should take concerted efforts in establishing a regional body called 'African Space Agency,' that will regulate emerging space actors within the region as well as to harness the lofty benefits of space exploration for the benefit of Africa and humanity at large.

PROFILE

Agbadi Mustapha Eleyawa is a 24 year old graduate of Law from the prestigious Kogi State University, Anyigba and currently a student of the Nigeria Law School. He is an aspirant to the Nigerian Bar who sat for the 2016/17 Nigerian Law School Bar Final Examinations for qualification into the reputable Nigerian Bar Association and have successfully passed the examination. He is currently awaiting his Call to Bar Ceremony later in November 2017.

In December 2015 he wrote his long essay titled 'International Legal Limitations and Contemporary Issues in the Use and Exploration of Outer Space' which was supervised by Prof. Jimmy O. Chijioke a renowned scholar in the field of International Law. Mustapha is currently a member of African Youth Initiative on Climate Change and serves on the selection board of African Youth Initiative on Climate Change (Nigerian Chapter). He believes that Space Exploration is the future for Africa as he is a strong Space Law Activist with the view that in order for Africa to become the next frontier in Global Space Industry the African Union (AU) needs to establish an African Space Agency that will harness and regulate Space Activities within the African Region.

INTRODUCTION

The first attempt by an African to land on the Moon was made in 1964 by a Zambian High School Teacher Edward Mukaka Nkoloso, who attempted to surpass the Union of Soviet Socialist Republic's (USSR's) and the United State of America in the race to land on the moon. Although he did not succeed, his ambitious idea gave rise to the numerous space programs that Africa boasts of today.¹

AN ANALYSIS OF THE TOP FIVE (5) SPACE FARING NATIONS IN AFRICA

1. SOUTH AFRICA: - is one of the top five (5) African Countries with an Advanced Space Program and also happens to be the first African country to have an Astronaut in Outer Space.² Thus, it has had a long history in Outer Space, beginning with the establishment of the first Southern Hemisphere Astronomical Observatory in 1820.³

Furthermore, the **South African National Space Agency (SANSA)** is they key regulatory agency of South Africa Space Program as it was established on the 9th day of December 2010.⁴ Hence, SANSA derives its mandate from the SANSA Act ⁵ in order to Promote the Peaceful Use of Outer Space, Foster International Cooperation in Outer Space Related Activities and to Create an Environment Conducive for Industrial Development in Outer Space Technology by Focusing on Human Capacity Development, Infrastructural Development and Outreach Programmes.⁶ Although, SANSA stated value proposition is to create create a societal, intellectual, human, economic and global capital in the global space industry as it's major focus is streamlined towards these six (6) constituent:

- ◆ Earth Observation.
- ◆ Space Operations.
- ◆ Space Engineering.
- ◆ Space Advancement.
- ◆ Public Engagement.
- ◆ Human Capital Development.⁷

1 Fredrick N., "Top 5 African Countries with Advanced Space Programs." Available at <https://face2faceafrica.com/article/top-5-african-countries-advanced-space-programs.html>

2 Shabangu S., "From township to space, the world's first black African astronaut." Available at <https://www.brandsouthafrica.com/people-culture/people/from-township-to-space-the-world-s-first-black-african-astronaut.html>

3 Alan W.H., *Parallax: The Race to Measure the Cosmos* (New York: Dover Publication, Inc., 2013) at p.196.

4 SANSA., "SANSA Space Science History." Available at <https://www.sansa.org.za/spacescience/history.aspx>

5 South African National Space Agency Act 2008 (Act No. 36 of 2008)

6 South Africa, South African National Space Agency, About Us_Mandate and Objectives., <http://www.sansa.org.za/mandate-and-objectives.aspx>

7 Graham G., "An Analysis of the Space Policies of the Major Space Faring Nations and Selected Emerging Space Faring Nations." Available at <http://www.spacepolicyonline.com>

However, the major challenges facing the SANSA was identified at the International Astronautical Congress held in Cape Town in October 2011 where the then Head of SANSA who listed them as follows:

- ◆ Capital Building
- ◆ Indigenous Design, Manufacturing and Operations
- ◆ Explaining the Benefits of Space Activities to Politicians
- ◆ Balancing Near-Term Priorities with Longer-Term Returns.⁸

2. NIGERIA: - is one of the top five (5) African Countries with an Advanced Space Program as well as one of the largest economy in Africa. Thus, the regulatory agency for Nigeria's space program is the **National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA)**, which is part of the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology and it is overseen by the National Council on Space Science Technology.⁹ The Agency was established by the Obasanjo administration with the primary objective of establishing a fundamental policy for the development of space science and technology.¹⁰ Moreover, NASRDA has so far launched five (5) satellites that are used for various tasks, including performing environmental and scientific studies in the larger Niger Delta Region and locating Boko Haram Terrorists (BHT) in the North East Region.¹¹

Furthermore, the first satellite launched by NASRDA was the 'NigeriaSat-1' an earth observation satellite in 2003 and it lasted until 2012, four years longer than was expected. It was succeeded by other earth observation satellites 'NigeriaSat-2' and 'NigeriaSat-X' in 2011, as the latter was designed and built by Nigeria Engineers under the supervision of Surrey Space Technology Limited (SSTL).¹² In 2007, Nigeria joined the committee of nations with communication satellites following the launch of her Chinese built communication satellite 'NigComSat-1'. The satellite was however replaced with 'NigComSat-1R in 2011 following the de-orbiting of 'NigComSat-1' due to power failure a year after it was launched.¹³

Conclusively, NASRDA have effectively carried out its national regulatory responsibility expected of it in Outer Space in a bid to reduce the existing technology gap that has made Nigeria a consumer nation since its independence. Thus, its laudable achievements have made Nigeria rank

8 Comments By Sandile Malinga, Chief Executive Officer, South African National Space Agency during Plenary Event 9: South Africa and African Space Activities, International Astronautical Congress, Cape Town, South Africa, October 2011.

9 Ann G.D., *et al.* (Eds.) *Handbook of Space Engineering, Archaeology and Heritage* (New York: CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group., 2009) at p.976.

10 Sec. 1 National Space Research and Development Agency Act 2010.

11 Fredrick N., *Op. cit.*

12 Mohammed S.O., "Space Technology as a Strategic Tool for National Development." *Kogi State University, Anyigba Convocation Lecture*, (2015).

13 *Ibid.*

amongst the leading Space Faring Nation in Africa.

3. EGYPT: - in an attempt to take its space ambitions a notch higher, Egypt recently partnered with neighboring Sudan to launch several space programs as it endeavors to build an overall African Space Agency.¹⁴ Hence, Egypt has four (4) satellites, the first of which was launched in 1998. Although, these satellites are used for ground analysis and dedicated for agricultural purposes around the Nile region by observing the country's mainland and coastal line and also taking high resolution pictures for environmental, scientific and security purposes.¹⁵

4. ALGERIA: -In 2002 Algeria decided to import a space program and create a space agency called Algerian Space Agency (ASAL) with goal to launch 10 satellites into space by 2017.¹⁶ The Algerian Space Agency is a national public institution specific character, with legal personality and financial autonomy. It was created to design and implementation of the Algerian national space policy in a bid to develop its space activity as its main objective is to make the space tool a powerful vector of economic, social and cultural development and to ensure the safety and well-being of the national community.

Furthermore, the Algerian Space Agency (ASAL) has the following duties and responsibilities:-

- ◆ Propose to the government the elements of a national strategy in the field of space activities and ensure implementation;
- ◆ Implement a spatial infrastructure to build national capacities;
- ◆ Implement the annual and multi-annual programs for the development of national space activities related to the various sectors concerned and to ensure the monitoring and evaluation;
- ◆ Propose to the Government space systems best suited to national concerns and to ensure, on behalf of the state, their design, implementation and operations;
- ◆ Propose to government bilateral and multilateral cooperation policy tailored to national needs;
- ◆ Monitoring and evaluation of obligations from state obligations to regional and international agreements in the fields of space activity.¹⁷

Conclusively, the Algerian Space has flown five (5) different satellites in the facilitation of scientific research and telecommunication with the hopes to use its space technology to improve its social and economic development.

14 Fredrick N., *Op. Cit.*

15 *Ibid.*

16 John P., "Algerian Space Agency." Available at <https://www.globalsecurity.org/space/world/algeria/agency.html>

17 *Ibid.*

5. GHANA: - The Ghanaian space program is the youngest in Africa, only having been established five years ago. Despite its dawdling progress, the program is a representation of the country's big ambitions. It is operated by the **Ghana Space Science and Technology Center (GSSTC)**, whose main tasks is to coordinate research across the West African country in key areas such as satellite communications and remote sensing. However, the Ghana Space Science and Technology Center (GSSTC) plans to launch its first satellite in 2018.¹⁸

AN ANALYSIS OF THE AFRICAN SPACE POLICY AND STRATEGY OF 2016

The African Space Policy was adopted at the First Ordinary Session of the Specialised Technical Committee on Education, Science and Technology (STC-EST) of the African Union (AU), which took place between the 27th - 30th October 2015.¹⁹ Hence, the joint (STC-EST) meeting which was centered on Linking Education to Research and Innovation aimed at taking stock of the progress the African continent has made in education, science and technology as well as further deliberations and contributions towards attaining the AU Agenda 2063.

Furthermore, the STC-EST was an amalgamation of two African Continental Ministerial Gatherings that comprises of the African Ministerial Conference of Science and Technology (AMCOST) and the Conference of Ministers of Education of the African Union (COMEDA) that previously met every two years.²⁰ Thus, the Space Policy has two overarching goals namely:

- ◆ To use space science and technology to improve the quality of life and generate wealth in Africa.
- ◆ To develop and maintain African infrastructure and capacity to service both African and foreign markets in a responsible way.

In addition, the African Space Policy of 2016 is centered around the creation of an African Space Programme which will bring about all space activities in Africa under a common umbrella as well as providing training for regional space-related experts and partnerships to ensure that resources are used optimally.²¹ Thus, the policy emphasises the value of nurturing a strong space industry in

18 Fredrick N., *Op. Cit.*

19 HRST., "First Ordinary Session of the Specialised Technical Committee on Education, Science and Technology." Available at <https://au.int/en/newsevents/27670/first-ordinary-session-specialised-technical-committee-education-science-and.html>

20 Nordling L., "Bringing Science and Development Together Through News and Analysis." Available at <http://www.scidev.net/global/policy/analysis-blog/africa-analysis-the-continent-s-bold-spacy-policy-1.html>

21 *Ibid.*

Africa that will make sure that investments are directed at space technologies that is autochthonous and can positively affect the African market and stimulate growth. However, it also envisage the need for the continent to draw up its own regulatory framework for space technologies and also taking cognisance of International Treaties and Agreements.

On the other hand, the African Space Strategy of 2016 takes the overarching policy goals of the African Space Policy and suggests more concrete ways in which they can be achieved. Hence, it identifies the strengths of the African continent which includes:-

- ◆ Pockets of expertise and Strong Political Will as well as weaknesses such as Disparities in Space Expertise Across the Continent.
- ◆ Over-reliance on Technology from Abroad and Brain Drain.²²

Furthermore, the strategy sets out projected outcomes such as governance elements for the Space Programme should be in place along side various Regional Centers of Excellence within a year of implementation. Thus, it is envision that after five (5) years the Continental Space Programme should be fully established and that after ten (10) years it should be ranked among the top ten globally.²³ Although, the strategy also identifies indicators that can be used to measure whether continental ambitious in space are achieved as these includes: -

- ◆ The number of space-related indigenous patents and academic articles.
- ◆ The number of graduates in space-related fields.
- ◆ The number of orbital slots obtained for Africa-built or Africa-designed Satellite
- ◆ The level of long-term funding secured for space applications.²⁴

A PROPOSAL FOR AN AFRICAN SPACE AGENCY

It has been postulated that one avenue through which the African Regional Cooperation can be effectively harnessed is through the established of an 'African Space Agency' that will manage and coordinate the African Regional Space Program and also implement the African Space Policy and Strategy of 2016 with the view to attaining the African Union (AU) Agenda 2063.

22 Nordling L., *Op. Cit.*

23 *Ibid.*

24 *Ibid.*

Although, in August of 2010, the African Union (AU) Ministers of Communication and Information Technology called for the African Union Commission to conduct feasibility study for the establishment of such an agency to be called 'AfriSpace' through funding from the European Union (EU) of which a European Consortium undertook the study and made its recommendations as well as creating a road-map for the establishment of the Agency.²⁵ Hence, it is further believed that an African Space Agency will enable the African Continent to negotiate better offers for satellite construction, space launches, technology transfer, share of data, scarce facilities and infrastructures much more than individual small countries can do on their own.²⁶

Although, the initial African Union (AU) draft strategic plan for 2014-2017 laid further emphasis of the need to establish a Space Agency and the development of an African Space Policy with a view to hold a Convention by 2015 in order to establish an African Regional Space Agency to be called an 'African Space Agency'. However, further drafts stated that the 2015 goal was instead to develop Space Policy, Programmes and Strategic Pan-African Institution and Networks.²⁷ Thus, the above mentioned challenges have displayed the lack of political will, inadequate coordination as well as regulatory restrictions that has surrounded the actualisation of an African Space Agency.

CONCLUSION

Despite its meager resources in the technology sector, Africa appears to have a budding appetite for Advanced Space Technology as the dream in achieving an African Space Agency that will harness all available opportunities in Outer Space is still bleak notwithstanding the fact that critical issues such as funding, political will and sustainability needs to be addressed. I strongly believe that the role of African Youths in making Africa the next frontier in Global Space Industry can be achieved by canvassing for support from our various countries which will involve creating awareness on the opportunities that are available in space related field of studies *vis-a-vis* enlightenment of our political representative in various arms of government on the need to establish an African Space Agency that will harness and regulate Space Activities within the African Region for the benefit of Africa and humanity at large.

25 Timiebi A.J., "Realizing a Regional African Space Program." Available at http://swfound.org/media/205627/aganaba_timiebi_paper.pdf

26 Islam A.E., "Presentation on Policy and Strategy." 7th Space Working Group Meeting ; Sharm El-Shirk, Egypt (2015).

27 Timiebi A.J., *Op. Cit.*